

Data Collection Instrument: Interview Script

Part 1 – Research Introduction & Informed Consent

Interviewer to introduce themselves, welcome participant and thank them for joining.

Interviewer to explain the study purpose: “We’re exploring early ideas for tool features that may help threat hunters manage cognitive load and work more efficiently...”

Interviewer to confirm if the participant submitted the informed consent before continuing (sent before the interview session starts, so use less time only for a quick recap and verbally confirm the consent before starting).

The interviewer will briefly explain the structure of the session: “This interview is organized into five parts and is expected to take less than one hour. With your permission, the session will be audio/video recorded to support accurate transcription. Please note that all raw data will be accessible only to the University of Victoria research team, and the recordings will be securely deleted after transcription and analysis are complete.

Before we begin, do you have any questions or concerns about the process?”

Part 2 – Participant introduction & warm up

Interviewer to ask participants to introduce themselves and reflect on the definition of threat hunting based on their experience:

“Q1. To start, could you briefly introduce yourself? You’re welcome to share: (a) your name; (b) your current role; (c) How often you conduct or participate in threat hunting sessions

“Q2. Based on your experience and current work practices, how would you define the following?

a) Threat hunting as an activity — what does it involve in your context?

b) Threat hunters — who typically performs this work, and what defines their role?

Part 3 - Concept Review & Discussion

Interviewer to walk through the novel approach under investigation (or show the demo video with concept/feature mockup and end-to-end scenario = same as online survey).

Interviewer to ask participants the following closed-ended questions: “Now, thinking back to your latest threat hunting sessions at your work, please indicate how much you agree or disagree with the following statements regarding the approach (concepts and ideas) presented in the demo.”. Using the “Polls/quizzes” feature in Zoom.

Design Heuristics 1 = “Navigation & Exploration”

“Q1-a. This approach would help you stay oriented as you move between related entities, events, or other data.”

“Q1-b. This approach would make it easier to retrace your steps or revisit key points in the investigation.”

Q1-c. Would you like to add any comments for the overall Navigation & Exploration criterion?—This is an open-ended question, and the interviewer will ask after giving the participant some time to answer the previous closed-ended questions.

Design Heuristics 2 = “Clarity & Sense-Making”

“Q2-a. This approach would help you form a clearer picture of what is happening.”

“Q2-b. This approach would help you organize scattered or ambiguous information into a coherent story.”

“Q2-c. This approach would be useful for identifying gaps or missing steps in your investigation.”

“Q2-d. Would you like to add any comments for the overall Clarity & Sense-Making criterion?—This is an open-ended question, and the interviewer will ask after giving the participant some time to answer the previous closed-ended questions.

Design Heuristics 3 = “Decision Support”

“Q3-a. This approach would help you decide what to investigate next”

“Q3-b. This approach would support you in deciding when to shift focus, pause an investigation, or escalate a finding.”

“Q3-c. Would you like to add any comments for the overall Decision Support criterion?—This is an open-ended question, and the interviewer will ask after giving the participant some time to answer the previous closed-ended questions.

Design Heuristics 4 = “Communication & Handover”

“Q4-a. This approach would make it easier to explain your reasoning to another threat hunter (peer).”

“Q4-b. This approach would make it easier to explain your reasoning to a manager or client.”

“Q4-c. This approach would be useful to collaborate with another threat hunter or team during an investigation.”

“Q4-d. Would you like to add any comments for the overall Communication & Handover criterion?—This is an open-ended question, and the interviewer will ask after giving the participant some time to answer the previous closed-ended questions.

Design Heuristics 5 = “Memory & Mental Load”

“Q5-a. This approach would reduce the amount of information I normally memorize or track manually during my investigation.”

“Q5-b. This approach would support me to build and externalize my mental model of an investigation in progress.”

“Q5-c. This approach would make it easier to ‘pick up where I left off’.”

“Q5-d. Would you like to add any comments for the overall Memory & Mental Load criterion?—This is an open-ended question, and the interviewer will ask after giving the participant some time to answer the previous closed-ended questions.

Design Heuristics 6 = “Overall Perception”

“Your overall perception of the approach presented in the demo.”

“Q6-a. I would find this approach useful for my threat hunting work”

“Q6-b. I would find this approach easy to use”

“Q6-c. I would use this approach if it were available in my tools.”

“Q6-d. Would you like to add any comments for your overall perception or about the above statements?—This is an open-ended question, and the interviewer will ask after

giving the participant some time to answer the previous closed-ended questions.

Next, the interviewer will continue with open-ended questions:

“Q7. If this approach (concepts and features shown in the demo) were integrated into your current threat hunting workflow, what (if anything) might make you hesitant to adopt it? Please explain any concerns or limitations you see in applying this approach to your threat hunting investigations.”

“Q8. What aspects of the approach shown in the demo would make you want to use it in your threat hunting work? Additionally, are there any other concepts or features you wish existed that would better support your threat hunting investigations?”

Part 4 – Demographic Questions

After the demo walkthrough and related questions, the interview will explain to the participant what this part of the interview session is about: “We completed the questions related to the demo walkthrough, and now you’ll be invited to answer a few optional demographic questions. These are intended to help us better understand your professional background and context, so we can interpret the study results more accurately.”

Section: “Professional Background”

“Q1. How many years of experience do you have in cybersecurity?”

“Q2. What is your current job title?”

“Q3. What is your typical working arrangement when performing threat hunting?”

“Q4. How often do you actively engage in threat hunting sessions as part of your work?”

Section: “Team and Collaboration”

“Q5. Do you typically work solo or in a collaborative threat hunting team?”

“Q6. How frequently do you need to explain or report your threat hunting investigation to others (e.g., threat hunter peers, cybersecurity analysts, clients or managers)?”

Section: “Tool Usage and Workflow Context”

“Q7. Which tools do you regularly use when conducting threat hunting activities?”

Please indicate the SIEM (Security Information and Event Management), UEBA (User and Entity Behaviour Analytics), EDR (Endpoint Detection and Response), Log analysis, or other top tools you use during threat hunting.

If you do not use any industry-standard tools in a given category, please indicate “None,” “N/A,” or specify if you use a custom or in-house solution.”

-SIEM tools (e.g., Splunk, QRadar, ...);

-UEBA tools (e.g. tools ArcSight Intelligence, Exabeam);

-EDR tools (e.g., CrowdStrike, SentinelOne);

-Log analysis or log forwarding tools (e.g., Elastic Stack, Graylog);

-It depends or other, Please specify.

“Q8. How often do you rely on external notes, bookmarks, or your memory during threat hunting investigations?”

“Q9. Do you use any personal tools or strategies to track or map your threat hunting investigations? Please describe what you use (e.g., mind maps, sticky notes, OneNote, diagrams, spreadsheets, etc.).”

“Q10. When you pause and later resume a threat hunting investigation, how do you keep track of where you left off? Please explain your approach (e.g., notes in OneNote, bookmarks in a tool, mental checklist, etc.).”

Complement or follow up:

“When conducting a threat hunting session, how do you build and externalize your mental model of this hunting investigation?”

“Which tools do you use during that process?”

“What challenges do you face?”

“What are the most frustrating or mentally exhausting parts of a typical threat hunting session?”

Section: “General (others and optional)”

“Q11 What is your highest level of completed education?”

“Q12. What is your gender?”

“Q13. Where is your organization’s headquarters, or if you are a consultant/self-employed, where are most of your clients based? (Please indicate the country)”

“Q14. If you work remotely in a different country than your organization or most of your clients (if you are a consultant or self-employed), please indicate your country.”

Part 5 – Closing

Interviewer thanks participant for joining the session and open for any final comments or questions: “Do you have any additional thoughts, suggestions, or feedback you would like to share? This can include anything about your threat hunting workflow, the concepts shown in our demo, or your experience in general.”

The interviewer closes the session by explaining the next steps of the study.